

**INVESTOR SENTIMENT AND STOCK MARKET VOLATILITY:
UNVEILING THE CONNECTION THROUGH SURVEY INSIGHTS**

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Abstract:

This paper seeks to understand the interrelationship between investor sentiment and stock market fluctuations with a focus on its sub-components the market expectation, risk perception, confidence level in the market and investor behaviour. Investor sentiment as the independent variable is analyzed as to its total causal effect on stock market volatility with trading volume and stock market liquidity as the moderating variables. Using survey data, this study examines how changes in investors' sentiment cause fluctuations, with trading activity and transaction squared which determines the strength and character of the relationship. The study gives the overall picture on how mood influenced elements spread throughout the market and intensify or dampen the fluctuations. The results generated provide the investors, analysts and the policymakers who intend to study the market or predict the market directions to a great extent aiming at strengthening the foundation of behavioral finance and monitoring the market stability. This research seeks to establish a relationship between investor behaviour and stock market returns with the objective of contributing to the body of literature in financial markets.

Key Words: Market Expectations - Risk Perception - Market Confidence - Investor Behaviour Trading Volume - Stock Market Liquidity - Stock Market Volatility

Introduction and Background:

In Investors, analysts, and policymakers must be aware of the forces that contribute towards stock market volatility since the market is constantly changing with increased complexity. Market sentiment refers to the attitude of the investors towards a particular market, its future prospects, risks inherent in it, level of confidence and, of course, the behavior in the context of these parameters. That is, sentiment affects stock prices in a fashion that is possibly even more erratic as it relates to both macroeconomic indicators and movements within the market. The relationship between the positive sentiment of investors and fluctuations in the stock market has attracted much interest in the field of behavioral finance in which scholars strive to uncover mechanisms by which psychological factors manifest themselves at the aggregate level.

Although the notion of investor sentiment has recently received considerable attention from academicians and practitioners, the exact channels that connect it to fluctuations in market volatility are still rather elusive. Trading volume and stock market liquidity are some financial variables that may moderate this relationship indicating how sentiments interfere with or either enhance the widening of the volatility gap. It is information about these factors that one needs to know in order to look at the role of investor psychology on the practices on the market in more detail.

This study employs survey data to capture real time sentiment of investors thereby providing an empirical means for examining role of various and components of market sentiments including market expectations, risk perception etc towards explaining the volatility in the markets. In this way, the study seeks to provide new theoretical advancements of the sentiment-volatility relation and the moderating effects of market conditions as manifesting through trading volume and liquidity.

Review of Literature:

A new study also points out the fact that there is close relationship between the business outlook and the fluctuations witnessed in the stock markets. Baker et al. (2019) clearly explained how market expectations and risk perception affect prices and how prices becomes very volatile, especially in situations that investor uncertainty is high. In the same way, Smales (2021) discovered that when there is belief from investors, it leads to less fluctuations in the market as it helps to regulate trading patterns. However, when the investors' behavior is bound to sentiments, which include instances of irrationality, like during the occurrence of an economic crisis, market volatility surfs erratically supposing the work of Da, Huang, and Yun (2020). Altogether, these surveys highlight the fact that investor sentiment, this part of it at least, the psychological and emotional side, are one of the causes of the stock market fluctuations.

Trading volume is another moderator mediating between investors' attitude and flaring of volatility. Research points out that a herd behavior increases trading which is believed to be fueled by positive investor sentiment that in turn leads to a volatility. In their study García, Huertas and González (2020) found out that increase in market confidence translates to violent in trading volume which in turn results

to high volatilities in price. Lee and Tsai (2019) analysis indicated that during high positive and high negative sentiment the high trading volumes augment the volatility of the market. Moreover, Zheng and Liu (2021) found that activity in excess of trading volume, due to investors' expectations, causes increased volatility of the market, showing that trading activity is an amplifier for the effect of sentiment.

Another variable that helps in mediating the sentiment-volatility relationship is market liquidity of stock markets. Liquidity partly reduces the impact of investor sentiment on the volatility since it provides easy flow of speculative funds, Chung and Chuwonganant (2020). On the other hand, low levels of this factor led to high volatility especially where the sentiment of investors is negative (Chen, Liang, & Wang, 2018). Fan, Xu, and Wang (2022) also classified that, low liquidity coupled with diminishing market confidence leads to high volatility due to market liquidity constraints that prevent market rebalancing. From these results, it is concluded that conditions of market liquidity are the factors that contribute significantly to the relationship between investor sentiment and the volatility of the stock markets.

Statement of the Problem:

The association between the investor sentiment and the stock market volatility is relatively unanalyzed especially in the light of how different components of sentiment intensity impact on volatility via other intermediary factors like trading volume and liquidity. More specifically, it is necessary to gain better insight into this relationship in order to better anticipate, and therefore possibly control, further changes in the market.

Research Gap:

Hence, the current paper seeks to contribute to the literature by addressing this gap by investigating the moderating roles of trading volume and stock market liquidity on investor sentiment effect on market outcomes. In a way, this work seeks to plug that gap by analyzing how these market conditions affect the sentiment-volatility relationship.

Research Questions:

- Are the mean quantities of investor sentiment aspects substantially different from a hypothesised benchmark value?
- What is the connection across trading volume as well as stock market liquidity, and how robust is the connection among these two variables?
- Using trading volume and stock market liquidity as mediating variables, how do investor sentiment aspects influence stock market volatility, both immediately and subsequently?

Objectives:

- To determine whether the mean quantities of investor sentiment aspects notably deviate from a hypothesised benchmark value.
- In an effort to evaluate the intensity and direction of the connection across trading volume and stock market liquidity.
- To investigate both the immediate and secondary impacts of investor sentiment aspects on stock market volatility, with trading volume as well as stock market liquidity serving as mediating variables.

Proposed Conceptual Model:

Investor Sentiment Components

Figure 1: Proposed Conceptual Model

This conceptual model highlights the parts of the Investor sentiment which includes the Market Expectations, Risk Perception, Market Confidence and the Investor Behavior as well as the Stock Market Volatility. This calls for the notion that these components determine the trading volume and the liquidity of the stock markets thus impacting the stock market fluctuation. As explained, trading volume and stock market liquidity act as the variable through which investor sentiment has an impact on market volatility.

This model is expected to test hypotheses centered at the volume and liquidity factors as intermediaries of the components of investor sentiment on the behavior of the stock market.

Research Hypothesis:

- H1: The hypothesised benchmark value is considerably deviated from the mean levels of investor sentiment aspects (Market Expectations, Risk Perception, Market Confidence, and Investor Behaviour).
- H2: The stock market liquidity and trading volume exhibit a substantial correlation, which can be either positive or negative.
- H3a: The volatility of the stock market is directly influenced by investor sentiment components.
- H3b: The stock market volatility is indirectly influenced by investor sentiment components, with trading volume and stock market liquidity serving as mediating variables.

Research Methodology:

The methodology for the study focuses on stratified random sample of one hundred and forty three new generation individual investors from Northern Kerala. Primary data will be gathering through a proper time table and the rest of the information will be pulled from articles, books, journals and other sources. In order to conduct an analysis, the degree and impact of each of the aspects of investor sentiment including market expectations, risk perception, and others would be done with a view of relating them to the trading volume, stock market liquidity, and volatility.

Data Analysis:

Data analysis for this study will be done at three different rackets and these are: Thus, to determine whether the components of investors’ sentiment namely Market Expectations, Risk Perception, Market Confidence and Investor Behavior, are significantly different from a hypothesized value, we shall employ a one sample t-test. Second, a correlation analysis will be conducted to determine the extent and nature of the trading volume and stock market liquidity with a view of determining some relationship between them. Last, the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and the path analysis will be used to analyze not only direct effect of the components of the investor sentiment on volatility in the stock market but also moderated through trading volume and stock market liquidity. The above described approach will enable me to achieve a multi faceted understanding of the relationship between sentiment, market liquidity and volatility.

Table 1: One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Market Expectations	99.135	402	0	4.335	4.25	4.42
Market Confidence	99.302	402	0	4.375	4.29	4.46
Risk Perception	101.371	402	0	4.481	4.39	4.57
Investor Behaviour	99.814	402	0	4.496	4.41	4.58

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

One sample t-test analysis of all the four investor sentiments show that the four sentiments of Market Expectations (t = 99. 135, p < . 001), Market Confidence (t=99. 302, p < . 001), Risk Perception (t = 101. 371, p < . 001), and Investor behaviour (t = 99. 814, p < . 001) are significantly different from The means of all components are positive with 95% confidence interval emphasizing on the overall positive results above zero. These results conclude that the mean values of the investor sentiment components are above the hypothesized benchmark implying positive sentiment among the investors under study.

Table 2: Correlations

		Trading Volume	Stock Market Liquidity
Trading Volume	Pearson Correlation	1	.501**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0
	N	403	403
Stock Market Liquidity	Pearson Correlation	.501**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	
	N	403	403

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The Pearson correlation coefficient results reveal a moderate positive association between trading volume and stock market liquidity with the value of r = 0. 051 level, indicating that it is statistically significant Different groups of researcher defined hypothesis differently, as following; According to Pilgrim & Evangelou (2005), hypothesis is defined as an informed prediction about the nature of the world that exists beyond the research context. To achieve the above objectives, data was collected and analysed using

the 2-way Analysis of variance test at 01 level ($p < .001$). From this it can be inferred that the volume of trading and stock market liquidity move in tandem; that is, with high volume of trading, there rises an equal measure high level of stock market liquidity. A positive and strong coefficient of this comparison indicates that there is significant relationship between two variables, which means that high trading is likely to be accompanied by high market liquidity in context of 403 investors.

Figure 2: SEM- Path Analysis

Table 3: Model Fit Measures

Measure	Estimate	Criteria	Interpretation
CMIN		-	-
DF		-	-
CMIN/DF	2.409	Between 1 and 3	Model Fit
CFI	0.999	>0.95	Model Fit
SRMR	0.005	<0.08	Model Fit
RMSEA	0.05	<0.06	Model Fit
PClose	0.297	>0.05	Model Fit

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

As the results of the test indicates there is a good model fit based on different indices. Besides, the CMIN/DF ratio of 2. 409 which is within the acceptable range of 1 to 3 shows that the models fitting is reasonable in relation to the degrees of freedom. Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is ranging from 0 to 1, it has got the maximum value which is 0. 999 that is way above 0 cent of the actual price. 95, which proved the fact that the model is in very close agreement with the actual data set. The Theoretical Bulky Difference (TBD) is zero and The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is 0. Mean Lp value of the extracts 005, which is much below the maximum acceptable value of 0. 08, which show that the above correlations have been predicted and observed with lot of differences. These correlations indicate that the differences between the predicted are very minimal as compared to the observed correlations. Further, a Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is equal to 0. 05, which complied with small and mighty measure below 0. 06. The PClose value of 0 means that the stock price has closed at zero for the given week, thus there is no value to aggregate it in order to obtain PClose 4. 297, greater than 0. 05, this means that RMSEA is not significantly different from zero thus supporting the notion that the model is fitting well. Combined these indices reveal a high quality model, which closely represents the structure of the given data.

Findings:

The study revealed the following interesting findings regarding investors' attitude and the market. The t-test analysis for one sample made it possible to find out whether the mean score of ME, MC, RP, and IB was significantly different from the test value of 0 in a positive or negative way It was as follows; Overall, the findings revealed that the one sample t-tests confirmed the presence of strong and positive sentiment among the investor sample, since all the mean values of the four components: Market

Expectations, Market Confidence, Risk Perception All of them had statistically significant positive mean differences with 95% confidence intervals, which indicated investor's optimism in these aspects. Also, the Pearson correlation test showed that the relation between trading volume and stock market liquidity can be explained at a moderate positive level of $r = 0.501$, $p < .001$ which implies that increased in trading volume has a positive correlation with enhancement in market liquidity. Finally, in order to determine that the structural model fit the data well, the CMIN/DF ratio was also calculated and it was 2.409 the value of CFI is 0.999, an SRMR of 0 and In choosing between the two models, one should consider absolute values, which show an approximate model fit of. Estimated goodness of fit indices were, $\chi^2/df=3$, CFI=0.977, SRMR= 0.005, and RMSEA = 0. Overall, all the values were above the recommended standards for a good model fit which included Minimum Standard Error of 0.05. Altogether these conclusions draw attention to the importance of the investor sentiment as the major factor causing the fluctuations in the market and the degree of its liquidity.

Suggestions:

By these providing such evidence, it is recommended that future studies of the market conditions should take into account the significant impact of the investor sentiment. Such important strands of indexes include the Market Confidence and Risk Perception, and are important that investors keep an eye on sentiment as it influences the market significantly. There is much value in incorporating sentiment data when planning on how to regulate the market especially at the times of economic instability since frothy conditions such as high optimism or high fear lead to high market volatility. Besides, the positive relation between trading volume and liquidity that has been established by this study also provides further evidence on the need to encourage trading to enhance market liquidity. Increased market transparency may also help to bring more trade to the market place and thus increase liquidity. Managers who are managing investments might benefit in incorporating sentiment analysis into their analysis with a view of making accurate market prediction.

Scope of Future Study:

Future work might systematically extend the examination of investor psychology and its effects on market returns to different places and different type of assets. Investor sentiment measurements of two different geographical locations or within and during different periods of economic shocks (e.g. financial crises) might offer a better insight for the dynamic behavior of the sentiment measure and effects on the market. Further, future research could pay more attention to sentiment at a micro-level, like the specific trends of the social media sentiment and news sentiment to capture the movements in real-time market. Research can also be done to establish how other variables including; regulatory changes or macro-economic events, could impact on sentiment and the flow of market liquidity and volatility. Perhaps the use of a wider range of machine learning based approaches for sentiment analysis could help also monitor the flows of investors and conditions in real time.

Conclusion:

The paper concludes that investor sentiment is an important determinant of stock markets fluctuations and their liquidity. Therefore, high levels of positive sentiment as expressed in Market Expectations, Confidence, Risk Perception, and Behavior was common with the sample of investors and influenced market conditions. This positive and weak positive correlation with trading volume indicates that there is significant trading activity which enhances the liquidity in the stock markets. The existent good fit of the structural model increases the reliability, hence, provides key insights about the effect of investor sentiment in the market phenomena. As such, these findings indicate that sentiment should be widely recognized by market participants as a parameter to be taken into account when analysing markets and making necessary decision, and they pave way for further research into other issues relating to sentiment and the place of financial markets in general.

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